

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPETENT GENERAL EDUCATION SYSTEM LEADERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10364266>

Abstract. *In the article, the socio-psychological characteristics of the leaders of the general education system with competence in management activities are comprehensively revealed from the scientific, theoretical and practical aspects, and the importance of management in the life of the society is systematically analyzed.*

Keywords: *management, leadership, competence, general education, socio-psychological characteristics, systematic analysis.*

During the years of independence, our country has developed in every way and has shown its beautiful and unique image as a country with a new look. Improving the management system for the independent country of Uzbekistan, which is on the path of sustainable development, training modern management personnel, selecting them, training, retraining them, regularly improving their skills, raising the knowledge levels specific to management to a higher level. The issue of creating the necessary conditions related to development is becoming an important factor of development.

In fact, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of the education system, which is the fundamental basis of the management process, to develop important areas of social development, to ensure its consistency and stability, and to gradually direct the graduates of the general education system to higher education. Development of a plan of measures, paying special attention to the support of students and young people, encouraging individuals with special talents, organizing the activities of leaders in management based on national values are some of the urgent issues that need to be resolved today. is considered

The object of the study is the characteristics of social and psychological competence of general educational institutions and their leaders.

The main task of the research is to find leading personnel with high quality theoretical knowledge, practical skills and high experience, potential, creative approaches, competitive management ability, social-psychological competence. consists of preparation. The main goal of the study is to effectively organize the management process in the educational system and train highly competent management personnel, ensure their future productivity, both theoretical and consists of preparing managers with practical knowledge.

Ensuring the implementation of the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" No. PD-134 of May 11, 2022 and the implementation of the Republic of Uzbekistan In accordance with the new legislation on education, in order to further develop the general secondary education system, the issues of education and training are defined separately:

- education is a systematic process aimed at developing the young generation in all aspects, forming their consciousness, spiritual and moral values and outlook on the basis of specific goals and socio-historical experience;

- education is a systematic process aimed at providing students with in-depth theoretical knowledge, skills and practical skills, as well as forming their general and professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and developing their abilities;

- participants of the educational process - learners, parents or other legal representatives of minor learners, pedagogical staff and their representatives;

- specialty - the name of a specific type of professional training that ends with the awarding of a qualification.

Revealing the essence of the mentioned general socio-psychological features of education and training will definitely determine the comprehensive effectiveness of the general education system in the future.

Based on the above-mentioned opinions, the main principles in the field of education are as follows:

- recognition of the priority of education;
- freedom to choose the form of education;
- non-allowance of discrimination in the field of education;
- provision of equal opportunities for education;
- inculcation of national and universal values in education and upbringing;
- humanitarian, democratic nature of education and upbringing;
- continuity and consistency of education;
- Compulsory eleven-year education and one-year preparation of children aged six to seven for general secondary education;
- openness of education to everyone within the framework of state educational standards and state educational requirements;
- uniformity and differentiation of the approach to the selection of educational programs;
- education throughout a person's life;
- guaranteed social protection of pedagogues in society;
- secular nature of the education system;
- promotion of knowledge, ability and talent;
- harmony of state and public management in the education system;
- openness and transparency in the field of educational activities.

Based on the essence of the "Law on Education" in the new version mentioned above, taking into account the requirements set in the "National Personnel Training Program", adapting modern management to the educational process today is a social relationship. It is important to achieve effective management that is reflected in the system according to its content. Therefore, in our society, it is considered necessary to create the necessary conditions for the development of literature, art and free creative activity in order for a person to fully demonstrate his abilities, talent and talent given by nature.

Based on the above-mentioned topical issues, effective management is understood as the most demonstrative form of the leader's social influence on the team of pedagogues. In this sense, it can be said that leadership is a set of social-psychological characteristics and human qualities

that can be seen in the influence that the pedagogue can give to the person himself, and then to others.

Based on the above-mentioned opinions, let's pay special attention to the concept of competence. If we rely on the definitions given by the scientists who have analyzed the concept of pedagogical competence: **Competence** means the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional skills, skills and talents.

Based on the many definitions given to the concept of competence, according to the results of our scientific research, it was determined with the aim of giving a new interpretation of the concept of competence. According to him:

Competence is the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, acquired experience, acquired skills and qualifications necessary for the implementation of professional activities by the relevant specialist on the basis of directions, and putting them in practice at a high level of precision and in their place. refers to the ability to receive llay.

Therefore, the effectiveness of the management process is definitely determined by the management skills of competent leaders. Of course, the most complex of management processes is the field of education. Because it is necessary to manage the pedagogical community on the basis of the correct direction based on the state approved curriculum, curriculum and regulatory and legal documents that have a scientific basis. This is one of the important conditions of management. Especially in the management of the pedagogical community, the behavior culture, organization, initiative, knowledge, creativity, idealism of the leaders, the ability to follow others are considered important. The most important thing is intellectual potential and human virtue, that is, it means that the leader creates an opportunity for others to reveal their abilities and demonstrate initiatives.

Based on the study of the management system through a systematic analysis of the results of the activity of the leaders of the educational system, it was decided to develop the following measures to improve their management efficiency and put them into practice. They are reflected in:

1. Improving the management of the educational system and regularly increasing its efficiency.
2. Simplification of problems in the management activities of the leaders as much as possible based on the requirements of the time.
3. Expanding the activities of leaders and assigning them from the center to localities, clearly defining the powers of leaders, taking into account their qualifications and personal qualities.
4. Development of a prospective development strategy of the educational institution.
5. To determine the level of suitability for management activities based on a systematic analysis, to determine the positive and negative image of the leader, including all functional areas, based on the analysis of the strengths and weaknesses.
6. Development and implementation of an information system that provides effective communication between managers and pedagogues-employees with socio-psychological competence.
7. Improvement by modernization of the mechanism of stimulating productive labor activity, management procedures and decision-making systems.

8. Improving the qualifications of leaders and pedagogues-employees through regular educational, spiritual and educational training and retraining.

9. To develop the team's creative approach to work, striving for innovation, research, initiative, factor and perseverance skills.

10 Selection of leading personnel, proper distribution of positions according to their abilities and placing them in their place.

In solving management problems, it is important that the educational system improves the socio-psychological competence of leaders and directs the activities of modern leaders within the framework of the law.

For this reason, special attention is paid to improving the practical possibilities of its development based on the identification of social and psychological factors that shape the competence of the leaders of the educational system.

In short, the pedagogues-employees working in general secondary educational institutions and the pupils taught by them must comply with the educational process stipulated in the charter of the institution in the normative legal documents related to education. The socio-psychological competence of leaders will be evident only if they effectively organize the management process based on existing procedures and rules. In addition, if the management process is organized on the basis of national values and on the basis of global experience, the development of the state and society will certainly be achieved.

All of these cases are related to the socio-psychological qualities of leaders with management competence, adherence to the rules of etiquette, standards of behavior established for employees, students and their parents based on national and universal values in a general secondary educational institution. is a process that depends on their compliance.

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